
Phase Formation and Properties of Phases in the Yb-As-Se Ternary System

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Abstract The character of chemical interaction in the Yb-As-Se ternary system was investigated by complex methods of physical-chemical analysis. The regions of the primary crystallization of the initial and obtained phases were detected. A number of physical-chemical, crystallochemical and chemical properties of the obtained phases were studied. All of the compounds obtained are prospective semiconductors with mixed chemical bonds.

Keywords phase diagram, ternary system, Yb-As-Se, glasses, semiconductors

Introduction

The simplicity of technology and determined high photosensitivity greatly increased application of chalcogenide glasses in optic electronics. It was of interest to give them a new property by introduction of the magnetic ion – a rare earth element into their composition. To solve the set problem, phase equilibrium in the Yb-As-Se ternary system has been investigated.

To find out the complete nature of chemical interaction in the Yb-As-Se ternary system together with the sections studied before, the following sections were investigated: $\text{YbAs}_4\text{Se}_7\text{-Se}$, $\text{As}_2\text{Se}_3\text{-Yb}_3\text{Se}_4$, $\text{As}_2\text{Se}_3\text{-Yb}_2\text{Se}_3$ and $\text{AsSe-Yb}_2\text{Se}_3$ [1-3]. Earlier in the Yb-As-Se system three congruent YbAs_4Se_7 , $\text{Yb}_3\text{As}_4\text{Se}_9$, YbAsSe_3 and incongruent compounds were found.

Experiment

The alloy synthesis of the system was carried out in a rotary oven from As_2Se_3 , YbAs_4Se_7 , AsSe , Yb_2Se_3 , Yb_3Se_4 and from ITM-1 Ytterbium and B-4 selenium elements. The synthesis consisted of preliminary holding at 650 K during 3-4 hours and the following heating to the required synthesis temperature. The initial components of sections are described in [1-3].

The plot of the phase diagrams of the sections mentioned above was constructed. The alloys synthesized before and after annealing were investigated by the methods of differential-thermal analysis (DTA), high-temperature differential thermal analysis (HDTA), X-ray diffraction analysis (XRDA), microstructural analysis (MSA) and determination of microhardness and density. DTA was carried out using two-coordinate self-recoding PDC-021 unit at the heating rate $9^\circ/\text{min}$, high-temperature VDTA-8_{2M} unit with Pt/Pt-Rh thermocouple. XRDA was carried out with the help of DRDM-3 unit with $\text{CuK}\alpha$ emission. MSA was carried out using the metallographic microscope MIM-7. Density was determined by picnometric weighing (bottle method) using toluene as a filler. Microhardness was measured with the help of PMT-3 microhardness meter with a loading of 10g.

Results and conclusions

The section $\text{YbAs}_4\text{Se}_7(\text{S}_1)\text{-Se}$ (fig.1) passes 2 determinate triangles $\text{YbAsSe}_3(\text{S}_3)\text{-As}_2\text{Se}_3\text{-S}_1$ and $\text{S}_3\text{-As}_2\text{Se}_3\text{-Se}$.

Figure 1: Phase diagram of the $\text{YbAs}_4\text{Se}_7(\text{S}_1)\text{-Se}$ system

The largest liquidus part of the section $\text{S}_1\text{-Se}$ 16,0-95,5 at.% is formed by the primary crystallization of β solid solutions on S_3 basis; while the smallest part, 96,5 - 100 at.% - by the region of primary crystallization of selenium. The region $L+\gamma$, where γ -solid solution is based on S_1 , occupies the intermediate part.

In the section, there are the following three-phase regions with participation of the liquid phase $L+\alpha+\beta$, $L+\gamma+\alpha$, $L+\gamma+\beta$, $L+\beta+\text{Se}$.

The region of primary crystallization $L+\beta$, as well as, the region of secondary crystallization $L+\alpha+\beta$ relate to both triangles intersected by the section.

In the system, the following peritectic reactions take place:

- 1) in the triangle $\text{S}_3\text{-As}_2\text{Se}_3\text{-S}_1$: $L+\alpha+\beta \leftrightarrow \alpha+\gamma$
- 2) in the triangle $\text{S}_3\text{-As}_2\text{Se}_3\text{-Se}$: $L+\beta \leftrightarrow \alpha+\text{Se}$

The section $\text{As}_2\text{Se}_3\text{-Yb}_3\text{Se}_4$ (fig. 2) crosses over 4 dependent triangles $\text{As}_2\text{Se}_3\text{-S}_1\text{-S}_3$, $\text{S}_1\text{-S}_3\text{-S}_2$ ($\text{Yb}_3\text{As}_4\text{Se}_7$), $\text{S}_2\text{-S}_3\text{-Yb}_2\text{Se}_3$, $\text{S}_2\text{-Yb}_2\text{Se}_3\text{-Yb}_3\text{Se}_4$.

Figure 2: Phase diagram of the $\text{As}_2\text{Se}_3\text{-Yb}_3\text{Se}_4$ system

The liquidus of the section consist of 4 fields of primary crystallization of phases: $L + Yb_2Se_3$, $L + \beta$, $L + Yb_3Se_4$, $L + \alpha(As_2Se_3)$; 8 fields of secondary crystallization $L + \alpha + \gamma$, $L + \alpha + \beta$, $L + \beta + \gamma$, $L + \beta + S_4$, $L + \beta + S_2$, $L + Yb_3Se_4 + Yb_2Se_3$. It is noteworthy that the field of primary crystallization $L + \beta$ is in three, but that of $L + Yb_2Se_3$ is in two dependent triangles.

Alloys of the section from 1,1 mol.% Yb_3Se_4 to 5,8 mol.% Yb_3Se_4 crystallize as $\alpha + \gamma$, 24,5-25,5 mol.% Yb_3Se_4 as $\beta + \gamma$, alloys 0-1,1 mol.% Yb_3Se_4 crystallize as α solid solutions correspondingly.

In the region from 5,8 to 24,5 mol.% Yb_3Se_4 a tertiary crystallization $\alpha + \beta + \gamma$ takes place, for the alloys with concentration 24,5-32,6 mol.% Yb_3Se_4 the following eutectic reaction $L + \beta \leftrightarrow \beta + \gamma + S_4$ takes place. The lowest eutectic horizontal of the section – 465 K is within concentrations from 37,5 mol.% Yb_3Se_4 to 60,0 mol.% Yb_3Se_4 and the corresponding eutectic reaction is $Yb_2Se_3 + L \leftrightarrow \beta + S_2 + Yb_2Se_3$. Alloys 32,6-37,5 mol.% Yb_3Se_4 of this section crystallize according to the peritectic reaction $L + \beta + S_2 \leftrightarrow \beta + S_2 + S_4$ alloys with concentrations from 60-100 mol.% crystallize in the form of mixture $Yb_3Se_4 + Yb_2Se_3 + S_2$.

The section $AsSe-Yb_2Se_3$ (fig.3) intersects three dependent triangles of system $Yb-As-Se$, namely $AsSe-S_2-YbSe$, $YbS_3-S_2-Yb_3Se_4$, $Yb_3Se_4-S_2-Yb_2Se_3$.

Figure 3: Phase diagram of the $AsSe-Yb_2Se_3$ system

The phase $L + Yb_2Se_3$ (42,9-100 mol.% Yb_2Se_3) forms the largest part of liquidus of the section. The phase $L + \sigma$, which is in three dependent triangles at once is almost commensurable with it. The liquidus region formed by δ solid solutions in comparison with that based on σ solid solution is only within the range 0-7,3 mol.% Yb_2Se_3 . There are three regions of secondary crystallization: $L + \delta + \sigma$, $L + \sigma + \eta$, $L + \sigma + Yb_2Se_3$.

Crystallization of alloys 42,9-100 mol.% Yb_2Se_3 takes place according to the eutectic reaction $L + \delta \leftrightarrow \sigma + Yb_2Se_3$.

The alloys of a triangle $YbSe-S_2-Yb_3Se_4$ crystallize into a mixture consisting of two solid solutions $\eta + \delta$. The eutectic horizontal $\eta + \sigma + \delta$ is the lowest eutectic in the system $AsSe-Yb_2Se_3$ – 530 K. Alloys of the system to 0,5 mol.% Yb_2Se_3 crystallize as σ solid solution, but in the region 0,5-4,3 mol.% Yb_2Se_3 the alloys solidify into a mixture $\sigma + \delta$.

The ternary system was triangulated by using data of methods of physical chemical analysis of quasi-binary systems. The indicated system is divided by the triangulating secants into 14 dependent triangles AsSe-Yb₂Se₃-S₂, As₂Se₃-S₁-S₂, AsSe-As₂Se₃-S₁, As₂Se₃-S₁-S₃, S₂-Yb₂Se₃-Yb₃Se₄, S₃-Yb₂Se₃-Se, S₃-As₂Se₃-Se, YbAs-AsSe-As, YbAs-YbSe-Yb₄Se₃, Yb₄Se₃-YbSe-Yb, S₂-S₃-Yb₂Se₃, S₁-S₂-S₃, S₂-YbSe-Yb₃Se₄, S₃-Yb₂Se₃-Se.

On the basis of literature and experimental data, the projection of liquidus surface of the system Yb-As-Se (Fig.4) was plotted.

Figure 4: Liquidus projection of the Yb-As-Se system with isothermal lines

The liquidus of the system consists of 3 fields of primary crystallization of phases: 1- α , 2- β , 3- γ , 4- δ , 5- η , 6- σ , 7- S₄, 8- Yb₂Se₃, 9- Se, 10-Yb, 11- Yb₅As₃, 12- Yb₄Se₃, 13- YbAs and As.

Due to the high partial pressure of arsenic vapours the subordinate *triangle* YbAs-As-AsSe was not studied, therefore, the boundary of the regions YbAs and As was not set. As a result, the regions of these phases coincide in the diagram. In the system Yb-As-Se, the character of mono- and non-variant progresses was studied. The characteristic points, their coordinates and reactions taking place in Yb-As-Se system are given in tables 1,2.

Table 1: Coordinates of double and ternary eutectic and peritectic points in the Yb-As-Se system.

№	Point symbol	Co-ordinate of a point. at. %		
		Yb	As	Se
1	2	3	4	5
1	e ₁	5.5	35.5	58.9
2	e ₂	4.9	40.3	54.8
3	e ₃	10.5	31.5	58.5
4	e ₄	-	20.0	80.0
5	e ₅	4.2	4.2	91.7

6	e ₆	12.5	30.0	57.5
7	e ₇	19.2	22.5	58.1
8	e ₈	21.0	19.0	60.0
9	e ₉	19.7	23.5	56.8
10	e ₁₀	19.3	24.6	56.1
11	e ₁₁	10.9	35.3	53.7
12	e ₁₂	41.7	-	58.2
13	e ₁₃	19.6	24.0	56.2
14	e ₁₄	5.5	44.5	50.5
15	e ₁₅	-	46.0	54.0
16	e ₁₆	1.5	48.5	50.0
17	e ₁₇	50.0	25.0	25.0
18	e ₁₈	56.1	43.9	-
19	e ₁₉	55.0	30.0	15.0
20	e ₂₀	64.2	35.8	-
21	e ₂₁	-	55.0	45.0
22	p ₁	4.0	36.0	60.0
23	p ₂	13.4	29.5	58.0
24	p ₃	58.9	41.9	-
25	E ₁	2.1	0.6	97.2
26	E ₂	11.7	30.1	58.2
27	E ₃	19.9	22.1	58.0
28	E ₄	20.1	23.5	56.4
29	E ₅	11.2	36.6	52.9
30	E ₆	8.7	36.0	55.2
31	E ₇	4.4	40.4	55.5
32	E ₈	2.9	48.5	48.5
33	E ₉	54.4	32.2	13.3
34	E ₁₀	64.0	35.9	0.3
35	P ₁	0.8	32.8	66.4
36	P ₂	15.1	26.6	58.3
37	P ₃	10.3	35.0	54.7
38	P ₄	6.6	34.4	59.0
39	P ₅	52.3	47.4	1.5

Table 2: The character of proceeding of monovariant and nonvariant processes in the Yb-As-Se system

№	Curve symbol	The nature of chemical interaction	Temperature, K
1	p ₁ P ₄	L+β↔α	870→630
2	e ₃ P ₄	L↔γ+β	720→630
3	P ₄ e ₁	L↔α+γ	630→590
4	P ₁ e ₄	L↔α+Se	420→415
5	p ₁ P ₁	L+β↔α	870→415
6	e ₅ P ₁	L↔β+Se	470→415
7	e ₃ E ₂	L↔γ+β	720→635
8	e ₇ P ₂	L↔η+β	690→635
9	p ₂ P ₂	L+η↔S ₄	1000→665
10	e ₆ E ₂	L↔S ₄ +γ	870→635
11	P ₂ E ₂	L↔S ₄ +β	660→635
12	e ₇ E ₃	L↔η+β	690→465

13	e_9E_3	$L \leftrightarrow Yb_2Se_3 + \eta$	1050→465
14	e_8E_3	$L \leftrightarrow Yb_2Se_3 + \beta$	750→465
15	$e_{12}E_4$	$L \leftrightarrow \delta + Yb_2Se_3$	1250→615
16	e_9E_4	$L \leftrightarrow Yb_2Se_3 + \eta$	1070→615
17	$e_{13}E_4$	$L \leftrightarrow \eta + \delta$	1050→615
18	$e_{14}E_5$	$L \leftrightarrow \sigma + \delta$	550→530
19	$e_{11}E_5$	$L \leftrightarrow \eta + \sigma$	540→530
20	$e_{10}E_5$	$L \leftrightarrow \delta + \eta$	1090→530
21	$e_{11}P_3$	$L \leftrightarrow \eta + \delta$	540→470
22	p_2P_3	$L + \eta \leftrightarrow S_4$	1000→470
23	$e_6 E_6$	$L \leftrightarrow S_4 + \gamma$	870→450
24	P_3E_6	$L \leftrightarrow \delta + S_4$	470→450
25	$e_2 E_6$	$L \leftrightarrow \delta + \gamma$	540→450
26	$e_2 E_7$	$L \leftrightarrow \delta + \gamma$	540→490
27	$e_{15}E_7$	$L \leftrightarrow \delta + \alpha$	545→490
28	e_1E_7	$L \leftrightarrow \gamma + \alpha$	590→490
29	$e_{10} e_{13}$	$L \leftrightarrow \eta + \delta$	1090→1070
30	$e_{14}E_8$	$L \leftrightarrow \sigma + \delta$	550→407
31	$e_{16}E_8$	$L \leftrightarrow YbAs + \delta$	520→407
32	$e_{17}E_8$	$L \leftrightarrow YbAs + \sigma$	2000→407
33	$e_{17}E_9$	$L \leftrightarrow \sigma + YbAs$	2000→1370
34	$e_{18}E_9$	$L \leftrightarrow YbAs + Yb_4Se_3$	1620→1370
35	$e_{19}E_9$	$L \leftrightarrow \sigma + Yb_4Se_3$	1450→1370
36	$e_{19}E_5$	$L \leftrightarrow Yb_4As_4 + \delta$	1450→1438
37	p_3P_5	$L + Yb_4Se_3 \leftrightarrow Yb_5Se_3$	1685→1438
38	P_5E_{10}	$L \leftrightarrow Yb_5Se_3 + \delta$	1438→856
39	$e_{20}E_{10}$	$L \leftrightarrow Yb_5Se_3 + Yb$	880→856
40	YbE_{10}	$L \leftrightarrow Yb + \delta$	1097→856
41	SeE_{10}	$L \leftrightarrow Se + \delta$	490→470
42	E_1	$L \leftrightarrow Se + \beta + Yb_2Se_3$	470
43	E_2	$L \leftrightarrow \beta + \gamma + S_4$	640
44	E_3	$L \leftrightarrow \eta + \beta + Yb_2Se_3$	690
45	E_4	$L \leftrightarrow \eta + Yb_2Se_3 + \delta$	615
46	E_5	$L \leftrightarrow \sigma + \delta + \eta$	530
47	E_6	$L \leftrightarrow \delta + \gamma + S_4$	450
48	E_7	$L \leftrightarrow \alpha + \gamma + \sigma$	490
49	E_8	$L \leftrightarrow \sigma + \delta + YbAs$	407
50	E_9	$L \leftrightarrow \sigma + YbAs + Yb_4As_3$	1370
51	E_{10}	$L \leftrightarrow \sigma + Yb + Yb_5As_3$	856
52	P_1	$L + \beta \leftrightarrow \alpha + Se$	420
53	P_2	$L + \eta \leftrightarrow S_4 + \beta$	660
54	P_3	$L + \eta \leftrightarrow S_4 + \sigma$	470
55	P_4	$L + \beta \leftrightarrow \gamma + \alpha$	630
56	P_5	$L + Yb_4As_3 \leftrightarrow Yb_5As_3 + \sigma$	1438

Conclusion

The largest liquidus region of the Yb-As-Se ternary system is formed by σ solid solution on the basis of YbSe and Yb_4Se_3 (49.5 wt.% of Yb-As-Se triangle) the smallest one falls within 3 regions: S_4 , Yb_5Se_3 , Yb (0.2 wt.% of Yb-As-Se triangle). The glasses occupy 1.88 wt.% of triangle's total area.

The glasses are not dissolved in mineral acids, as HCL and H₂SO₄, but they are well dissolved in concentrated nitric acid and alkali, as well. The values of such properties of glasses as softening temperature, density and microhardness grow with increase of the concentration of Yb in the composition of glasses.

The detected glasses are p-type semiconductors and their electroconductivity rises with growing ytterbium concentration. Both metallic Yb and its chalcogenides, probably, form polarons of small radius and transition into trivalent state is not excluded, conductivity in this case is realized at the account of jumps of charge carriers between ions of different valency and this favours the increase of electroconductivity [4-6].

On the basis of AsSe, As₂Se₃, S₁, S₂, S₃, YbSe, Yb₃Se₄ the regions of solid solutions have been discovered.

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